

Preparation and Structure of Some Bidentate Schiff Base Complexes of Copper(II)

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Complexes of copper(II) with bidentate Schiff bases derived from 2-OH-3-chloroacetophenone and the amines have been prepared. A trans square planar structure has been suggested for these complexes.

THERE has been considerable interest in the last few years in the electronic structure of planar complexes. In particular structural investigations on the metal complexes formed by Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde with transition metals have been reported¹⁻⁴. The object of this study is to synthesize some new copper(II) complexes with Schiff bases prepared by the condensation of 2-OH-3-Cl-acetophenone with amines like aniline, *m*- and *p*-toluidine. The complexes are characterized by i.r. and electronic spectra and magnetic measurements.

Experimental

The following Schiff bases were prepared by the method described earlier⁵.

where R = H (Ligand 1)
R = *m*-CH₃ (Ligand 2)
R = *p*-CH₃ (Ligand 3)

All complexes were prepared by the same general method. To a hot solution of the copper acetate in alcohol, solution of the Schiff base in the same solvent in the ratio 1 : 2 was added. The resulting mixture was refluxed for about 2 hr. The complex so obtained, was recrystallized from chloroform.

I.R. spectra in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹ were studied with Carl Zeiss UR-10 spectrophotometer. Absorption spectra were recorded at room temperature with a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer. The reflectance spectra were obtained by Venanzi's method.⁶ Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature by Gouy's method.

The complexes were analysed for their copper and nitrogen contents by the standard methods.

Results and Discussion

Based on the results of elemental analysis (Table 1), the complexes are formulated as Cu(3ClOHA-R)₂ where R = aniline, *m*-toluidine and *p*-toluidine.

The magnetic moments are normal and as expected for planar stereochemistry⁷.

Infrared Spectra

The chelate formation in all the complexes is suggested by their I.R. spectra as compared to those of the free ligands. These spectra provide important information about the ligand atom attachment to the copper ion. The tentative assignments of some of the important bands have been made and recorded in Table 2.

The characteristic features in the spectra are :

1. M-N and M-O bands observed at 510-525 cm⁻¹ and 470-475 cm⁻¹ respectively, provide the evidence for the formation of bonds between metal-nitrogen and metal-oxygen. There are no such bands in ligand spectra.

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA FOR Cu(II) SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Complex (amine used)	Colour	%Copper		%Nitrogen		μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
1. Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ONCl) ₂ (Aniline)	Dark-brown	11.08	11.48	4.80	5.06	1.71
2. Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ONCl) ₂ (<i>m</i> -Toluidine)	Brown	11.20	10.94	4.84	4.82	1.78
3. Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ONCl) ₂ (<i>p</i> -Toluidine)	Brown	10.92	10.94	4.85	4.82	1.73

TABLE 2. I.R. BANDS AND d-d BANDS OF COMPLEXES

Complex No.	I.R. (cm ⁻¹)				λ_{max} (nm)	
	C = N	Ph-C-O	Cu-N	Cu-O	Chloro-form solution	Reflectance*
1.	1590	1320	510	470	680	700 br
2.	1580	1330	520	475	680	680 br
3.	1580	1320	525	470	680	680 br

* Spectra of solid samples diluted with LiF.

- Stretching frequency of C = N mode which occurs at 1610 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand is shifted to lower values (1580 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of metal complexes indicating M-N bond formation. This is consistent with earlier observation⁸. However some workers have reported either no shift of C = N frequency⁹ or shift to the higher wave number on coordination.¹⁰
- A band in the region 1290 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand that may be assigned to Ph-C-O frequency is shifted to slightly higher (1320 cm⁻¹) values in metal complexes, indicating M-O bond formation. Similar observation has been also reported.¹¹

Electronic Spectra

The electronic spectral data of the complexes are given in Table 2. They are characterized by a broad

band in the region of 15000 cm⁻¹. This is the well-known d-d band of planar complexes.¹² A blank region between 10000 and 20000 cm⁻¹ is diagnostic of absence of tetrahedral complexes.

The above I.R. and electronic spectral data are suggestive of a trans planar coordinated environment for the central copper atom.

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References

- G. E. GURR, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 614.
- S. H. SIMONSEN and C. E. PELUGER, *Acta. Cryst.*, 1957, **10**, 536.
- N. S. BIRADAR and V. H. KULKARNI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* 1971, **33**, 2451.
- R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT, JR and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **7**, 83.
- A. SENIER and F. G. SHEPHEARD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 1950.
- G. DYER, J. G. HARTLEY and L. M. VENANZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1293.
- E. N. BAKER, D. HALL and T. N. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1960, 680.
- S. N. PODDAR and N. S. DAS, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 1105.
- B. D. SHARMA and J. C. BAILAR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5476.
- D. H. BUSCH and J. C. BAILAR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 1137.
- R. N. PRASAD and J. P. TANDON, *J. Inorg., Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1473.
- L. SACCONI and M. CIAMPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 276.